

A Study On The Determining Factors Of Employee Performance For Success In Transportation Services In Jordan's Tourism Industry

Hashem Tashtoush, Norlinda Mohd Rozar, Omar Shubailat, Bandar Ersan Alown, Aziz Madi

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: June 28, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: January 30, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Employee Performance, Employee Engagement, Transportation Services, Jordan</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5918944</p>	<p><i>Tourism and archaeological tourism industry contribute immensely to Jordan's economy. An organisation's strategy for success is based on individual employees' achievement, which in turn is directly based on their performance. Thus, it is necessary to investigate the factors that affect employee performance in the industry. The objectives of the study are to examine the relationship and the mediating relationship between the variables that were selected against employee performance in the tourism and archaeological tourism industry of the transportation services. A survey of previous studies and theories related to the subject of the study was conducted by a literature review and data collected by distributing 600 questionnaires to air transport, ground transport, and maritime transport workers who represent the majority of the three regions (North, Central, and South) in Jordan. The research objectives were achieved by analysis using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0 and PLS version 3.0. The result shows a positive relationship between the variables selected. This study provides insights into the impact of HRM on employee performance of tourism and archaeological tourism companies in Jordan with employee engagement in a mediating role. Finally, suggestions are offered on the impact of HRM on Jordanian tourism and archaeological tourism companies, and employee engagement to achieve employee performance.</i></p>

Introduction

The development and establishment of products and trade units have notably increased in order to boost economic growth in countries, with the tourism business taking top priority among them in the past few decades (Tashtoush, Rozar, Alown & Razik, 2021). Tourism is a significant industry that encompasses different infrastructure and services, and several nations have used educational institutions to support the sector's expertise in order for it to develop. Tourism has grown as one of the most important worldwide economic companies in the twenty-first century. Tourism may be described as the procedure of individuals or groups going from one location to another for pleasure or business.

Tourism is among Jordan's greatest and most important sources of foreign revenue. Jordan's tourist industry includes environmental and cultural tourism, adventurous and sports tourism, pilgrimage and religious sites, and national conservation areas (Alown, Mohamad & Karim, 2020). As according Masoud and Hmeidan (2013), the tourism sector has expanded to be one of the most major economic players in the world over the previous multiple decades, with the Middle East being one of the fastest growing areas. Tourism is a major economic engine in Jordan, and it is now the single greatest employer of workers. This significant industry includes a large number of infrastructures and service organizations. (Al Khattab & Aldehayyat, 2011; Almomani, Nasseef, Bataine, & Ayoub, 2017; AlWahaibi, 2016; Bazazo, Al-Dweik, Almomani & Alshatnawi, 2016).

Even though, there have some challenges, as at Figure (1, 2) shows that the years of 2009-2019, the ranking of Jordan on the TTCI reflected some serious deterioration. Indeed, in 2019, Jordan ranked 84th out of total of 140 economies, while the United Arab Emirates (UAE) scored best among the Middle Eastern countries. Jordan's rankings on the Travel & Tourism Sector have experienced deterioration in 12 out of the 14 pillars. The biggest drop lies in "Business Environment" (10 places), "ICT Readiness" (21 places), "Tourist Service Infrastructure" (15 places), and in "Human Resources & Labour Market" (37 places). Figure (1, 2) shows some of the main indicators for Jordanian tourism for the years (2009-2019). Jordan is confronted with the difficulty of coping with the spillover effect created by turbulence in neighboring countries, as well as the socioeconomic, political, and social pressures caused by the influx of a substantial percentage of Syrian refugees (Ghaith, Mutia, et al., 2018).

Figure 1: Ranking of Jordan on the Travel & Tourism Competitiveness Index, 2019.

Source: Jordan Strategy Forum (JSF) (2020).

Figure 2: TTCI Pillars Comparison in 2017 & 2019 for Jordan.

Source: Jordan Strategy Forum (JSF) (2020).

Jordan's transportation and logistics industry has grown significantly during the last decade, with aircraft traffic growing by more than 54% and passenger numbers more than doubling. Jordan's transportation and logistics industry offers significant investment potential, with an average annual growth rate of 5% to 6% up to 2030 and a variety of government projects. The tables below show the Transportation and Logistics Sector Indicators and growth performance (Department of Statistics, 2019, Ministry of Transportation 2019, Ministry of Labour 2019), and this means reasons to focus in tourism transportation service providers.

Table 1: Transportation and Logistics Sector Indicators

Total transport system exports (gross weight tons)	9,100,000
Maritime transport system exports (gross weight tons)	4,010,000
Air transport system exports (gross weight tons)	22,000
Direct contribution to GDP (%)	8.2%
Registered firms	325
Direct employment (%)	126,000

Sources: Department of Statistics, 2019, Ministry of Transportation 2019, Ministry of Labour 2019.

Table 2: Transportation Field

Growth Performance	2006	2019	Relative (%)
Aircraft movement	54,266	83,600	54.1%
Passengers	3,783,732	7,621,599	101.4%
Cargo and mail (tons)	99,214	105,768	6.6%

Since, found that the tourist transportation services have play an important role in tourism industry. It is responsible to accomplish tourism development in Jordan. The sphere of transportation in the tourist sector has been one of the key areas for the Higher Council of Tourism (HCT) since its inception in order to further tourism development plans. (Ministry of Tourism and Antiques, 2018). With hope that, the tourism industry in Jordan is expected to continue recovering during 2018 by more efforts to better promotion and open new markets for expansion (Faghieh, 2019).

Consequently, the potential of the market expansion of the tourism industry in Jordan has urges a more and deeper examination of employees in the industry (Ram & Prabhakar, 2011). As said by the study of Park &

Gursoy, (2012), the examination of employees in the industry have look into an engagement and its antecedents of employees. Furthermore, Employees are the backbone of every business's success, and they must be stimulated and retained at all costs in order for the firm to remain internationally competitive in terms of supplying excellent products and services to community.

Thus, for going to be more competitive have to develop and increase the role of transportation services in tourism, the countries should pay attention on staff development who are run and handling the services in transportation services for tourist. With the nature of tourism performance in Jordan as mentioned before, very important to have a well-developed and functional transportation system in Jordan. Means is a well-structured possibility of reaching various markets and providing the best quality service to the traveler. Consequently, the transportation services companies and the job performance of employee are the most important role for providing the best quality service to the traveler. In addition, the job performance was derived of by Human Resource Management practices (HRM) and leadership style.

Therefore, this study examines the role of HRM practices, and leadership style, in the Jordanian tourism industries of the employee performance and also in addition investigate the mediating role of employee engagement and since that currently was hard to find the study in the perspective of the transportation services in the tourism industry. As such, the research objectives are:

1. Do HRM and leadership style have a significant relationship with employee performance?
2. Do HRM and leadership style have a significant relationship with employee engagement?
3. Does employee engagement influence employee performance?
4. Does employee engagement mediate the relationship between HRM, leadership style and employee performance?

Literature Review

Employee Performance

employee performance is a practice that employees must engage in in order to successfully execute the task at hand (Dar, Akmal, Naseem, & Khan, 2011). According to Mukarram, Akbar, Jan and Gul (2012), performance ideas and requirements must also evolve to keep up with continuous organizational changes. The most essential function in achieving organizational success is the job performance of employees (Altangerel, Ruimei, Elahi & Dash, 2015). In other words, employee performance is critical in terms of both work and administration (Rizwan, Waseem & Bukhari, 2014). The most important seen factor in employee management has employee performance has traditionally been the most visible aspect in employee management. employee performance refers to what an individual does at workplace (Alown, Al-fakeh & Aburumman, 2021).

The mix of effort, abilities, and work environment types represents employee performance. In a rapidly changing economic and working environment throughout the world, organizational and personnel performance has become critical in order to remain competitive (Ling & Bhatti, 2014). As a corollary, it is critical for all organizations to examine the elements that influence employee performance (Yozgat, Yurtkoru & Bilginoglu, 2013). employee performance is recognized as the whole outcome that people provide to the organization. It is comprehensive in terms of ability, motivation, and opportunities (Ahmed, Warraich, Khoso & Ahmad, 2014).

HRM Practices

Starting with Pugh and Hickson (2016), an Honorary Professor of Business Administration at Harvard Business School delineates human resource management as one of the primary managerial activities involved in decision making and all decisions that influence the image of the employee-organization relationship. Human resource management is also described as a significant word that encompasses the policies, philosophies, techniques, and processes involved in managing employees within a company (Latorre, Guest, Ramos & Gracia, 2016). Furthermore, human resource management is defined as all actions connected to the administration of the workplace and workers in businesses (Armstrong & Taylor, 2020).

Employees are anticipated to perform poorly if they have bad opinions of HRM procedures, and vice versa. Employees' perceptions of HRM procedures are heavily impacted by the settings and places in which they work (Hatley et al., 2013). Likewise, Ekaterini, (2010) validates Wright et al. (1994) observations that the characteristics of the personnel and the management methods used to administer them have an influence on their performance. As a consequence, it is apparent that applying HRM practices in different locations, circumstances, and contexts yields varied results in terms of employee performance. As a basis, studies on the relationship between HRM practices and employee performance in Asian countries such as Jordan is anticipated to supplement existing knowledge in the new environment. Hence;

H₁: Human resource management practices has significant effect on employee performance in Jordanian tourist and archaeological.

Leadership style

Leadership style is amongst the most essential human resource-related deliverables, and perhaps one of the most investigated issues in management and industrial psychology. This is most likely related to the fact that leadership is a vital yet frequently contested topic in organizational research (Kesting et al., 2016; Puni et al.,

2014). Lewin, Lippitt and White (1939) recognized three primary leadership styles: democratic, authoritarian, and laissez-faire. Leadership allows businesses to become more productive and lucrative, but the amount of success is determined by the leader's style and the atmosphere provided for people to perform well. As per Asrar and Kuchinke (2016), Supervisors' leadership styles have a significant impact on organizational goals such as minimal employee turnover, reduced absenteeism, customer satisfaction, and organizational performance. As a corollary, leadership style affects interpersonal connections, rewards and recognition, as well as employee behavior, enthusiasm, and disposition, all of which have an impact on organizational success (Fiaz, Su & Saqib, 2017).

By several studies, the transactional leadership style is much more efficient than the transformational leadership style (Arham, Muenjohn & Boucher, 2012). Others found that transactional leadership is negatively connected to employee performance (Awamleh et al., 2005; Erkutlu, 2008), whereas Bass (1985) found that transactional leadership is essential for attaining positive employee performance. Hence;

H₂: Leadership style has significant effect on employee performance in Jordanian tourist and archaeological.

Employee Engagement

Employee engagement is the crucial focus being openly discussed by most practitioners and scholars currently because many aspects of this theme have yet to be studied and there are many different points of view on this matter (Harter & Blacksmith, 2010; Lee & Ok, 2016; Rothmann, 2017; Rothmann & Rothmann, 2010) even though it is associated with a variety of positive organizational outcomes such as increased customers' loyalty, increased productivity and profitability, and declined turnover of employees.

Employee engagement studies is not a new issue, with many investigations being conducted in certain countries across a wide range of sectors. Employee engagement, as per SheeMunet al., (2013) and Anaza and Rutherford (2012), was basically a matter supported by a variety of variables like as communication, decision-making empowerment, and supervisory support, rather than just the physical incentive aspects. Existing research, there is a favourable relationship between engagement and job aspiration (Geldenhuis, Laba & Venter, 2014). In other terms, employee engagement was exclusively focused on the employees and was the decider of how far the employees would be involved, depending on the aforementioned criteria. In contrast, employee engagement cannot be demonstrated if people identify potential opportunities outside of the present firm in which they are employed (Tiwari & Lenka, 2016). Employee engagement is defined by AbuKhalifeh and Som (2013) as a favourable attitude expressed by employees further towards the achievement of the organizational objectives.

Starting with Pugh and Hickson (2016), an Honorary Professor of Business Administration at Harvard Business School delineates human resource management as one of the primary managerial activities involved in decision making and all decisions that influence the image of the employee-organization relationship. Human resource management is also described as a significant word that encompasses the policies, philosophies, techniques, and processes involved in managing employees within a company (Latorre, Guest, Ramos & Gracia, 2016). Furthermore, human resource management is defined as all actions connected to the administration of the workplace and workers in businesses (Armstrong & Taylor, 2020).

As according Albrecht et al. (2015), an organization's HRM practices have a critical role in engaging employees in their job. Furthermore, the Centre for Human Resource Strategy (2009) contends that HRM practices are a critical driver in increasing employee engagement. Shuck, Rocco and Albornoz (2011) also offer a case study that demonstrates the positive relationship among HRM practices and employee engagement. Several investigations (Arakawa & Greenberg, 2007; Luthans & Peterson, 2002; Owor, 2016; Wagner & Harter, 2006) reveal that operators made significant changes to HRM practices in their businesses during the previous decade to assure high employee engagement levels. Likewise, Alfes, Truss, Soane, Rees and Gatenby (2013) and Krishnaveni, (2016) demonstrate that bad HRM practices such as unpleasant interactions between workers and employers, as well as hostile working behaviour, promote employee disengagement. Hence;

H₃: Human resource management practices has significant effect on employee engagement in Jordanian tourist and archaeological.

Leaders should understand which successful tactics enhance employee engagement in order to improve engagement (Kumar & Pansari, 2015). According to Saks and Gruman (2014), researchers have failed to come up with a clear definition of employee engagement, and scholars have failed to agree on leadership techniques that enhance employee engagement (Saul, Kim, & Kim, 2015). Irrespective of this disagreement, Farrell (2016) believes that corporate leaders and employee engagement are critical drivers of an organization's success. Leadership is required for engagement to occur (Howell, 2017). When Kahn (1990) stated that leaders ought to offer the proper atmosphere, psychological circumstances, and resources to guarantee participation, he was backed up by Farrell (2016) and Howell (2017). Leaders who may not promote and achieve employee engagement will find it difficult to develop and maintain a competitive edge (Nair & Salleh, 2015). Hence;

H₄: Leadership style has significant effect on employee engagement in Jordanian tourist and archaeological.

Several entrepreneurs struggle owing to a lack of commitment, as a devoted employee is essential for excellent employee performance (Oseiet al., 2017). Furthermore, regardless of the sector of work, it is obvious that excellent employee performance supports organizational success (Harter et al., 2002; Vosburgh,

2005). However, it is important to note that some components, such as ambition, are difficult to measure and must thus be extrapolated from behavior and body language in collaboration with responses (Sonsale, 2017). This makes assessing performance difficult as well. Wherefore;

H₅: Employee engagement has significant effect on employee performance in Jordanian tourist and archaeological.

Employee engagement was considered as a mediator impact between HRM practices and the employee performance relationship in this study. Almost little empirical research has been conducted prior to studying employee engagement as a mediator element in the link between HRM practices and employee performance in the context of Jordan's tourist sector (Ahmed, Hameed & Mahmood, 2016). Employee engagement is a relatively new concept in behavioural studies (Ellis & Sorensen, 2007; Macey & Schneider, 2008), very few studies in established contexts have been conducted taking into consideration employee engagement as a construct (Bailey, Madden, Alfes & Fletcher, 2017), but very few are discovered in developing contexts such as Jordan (Al-Tit & Hunitie, 2015). Therefore, in the perspective of ready-made garment industry in Jordan, employee engagement construct has been considered as a mediating role on HRM practices and performance relationship. Hence;

H₆: Employee engagement mediate the relationship between Human resource management practices and employee performance in Jordanian tourist and archaeological.

Scholars came to the conclusion that transformative leadership practices help to enhance an employee's level of engagement (Blomme, Kodden & Suffolk, 2015; Shepperd et al., 2014). Transformational leaders demonstrate the following behaviours that lead to employee engagement: (a) outstanding communication, (b) honesty and transparency, (c) a constructive job, (d) efficient and considerate direct supervisors, (e) career progression potential, (f) major contributor to organisational performance, (g) organizational glory, and (h) supportive colleagues (Liu & Zhang, 2015). Hence;

H₇: Employee engagement mediate the relationship between leadership style and employee performance in Jordanian tourist and archaeological.

Proposed Framework of the Study

The study attempts to develop a conceptual framework containing four components: HRM, leadership style (independent variables), employee engagement (mediating variable), and employee performance (dependent variable). The behavioural model illustrated in Figure 3 is proposed in this study.

Figure 3: Theoretical Framework

Research Methodology

This descriptive study depicts a phenomena or unique state that depicts the current situation and enables for making decisions. This type of study seeks to validate a previously defined theory. This study used a questionnaire survey to obtain primary data, and the respondents were chosen using a simple random sample approach. A total of 600 questionnaires were sent to employees working in Jordan's tourism and antiquities sites (Air transport, Ground Transportation and Maritime Transport). The replies and returned surveys from Jordan's

tourism and antiquities sites by area. Surveys distributed in North, for example, yielded 134 questionnaires. As an outcome, all 402 questionnaires issued were returned and used in this study.

In the questionnaires, constructed measurements from previous research were employed. The 7 items representing employee performance were adapted from Ahmad (2017), the 24 items chosen to represent HRM practices were adapted from Sabiu (2017), the 11 items indicating leadership style were adapted from Gaith & Mutia (2017), and the 5 items portraying employee engagement were based on Thilagavili, (2017). Each item was outfitted with a 10-point Likert scale.

This study carried out pilot test involving 130 questionnaires were sent to employees of Jordanian tourism and antiquities sites involved in air, ground, and maritime transportation. The justification for selecting respondents from this region is because they have a comparable background to the real respondents that were chosen for the study. A total of 113 surveys were returned, determining the clarity of the questions to the respondents, difficulties in replying, instructions clarity, layout attractiveness, and time necessary for questionnaire completion. The pilot study was carried out in February 2021 in a span of two weeks, during which 100 questionnaires were retrieved for the purpose of the pilot study as recommended by Awang, (2016). Table 3 has further statistics.

Table 3: Pilot Test Results

Construct	No. of Items	KMO	Cronbach's Alpha	Cumulative %	Sig.
EP	7	.871	.954	80.11	.000
HRMs	24	.931	.938	75.54	.000
LS	11	.809	.924	72.65	.000
EE	5	.755	.960	86.25	.000

This study ensured the validity and reliability of the questionnaire by soliciting input from qualified scholars (assistant professor at academic institutions) in order to make required adjustments to the questionnaire. Another stage in ensuring the validity and reliability of the questionnaire was to assess the internal consistency of the variables using Cronbach alpha. Hair (2017) recommended using a sample size of more than 100 to ensure the precision of the findings.

For data analysis, PLS-SEM software was utilized. As previously stated, a 10-point rating scale was employed, with 1 representing "strongly disagrees" and 10 representing "strongly agrees," and this range was acknowledged as appropriate by Awang, Afthanorhan and Asri (2015). Importantly, the interval scale has a continual score and meets the criterion for the use of parameterized statistical analysis. Numerous research has employed the 10-point rating scale, notably in structural equation modeling (Chen, 2013; Curseu et al., 2007; Delahaj et al., 2010).

Results

This study used a quantitative approach and used partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) to analyse the hypotheses and test the mediator and direct effects (Sarstedt et al., 2014). The model was analysed to assure the reliability and validity of the proposed measurement scales, using a two-stage approach: measurement model and structural model analyses (Hair et al., 2017).

Demographic profile

As per the table, there were 402 total respondents, with the bulk of them being male (64.4 percent), and the number of female respondents lagging behind (35.6 percent). In terms of age, the majority of respondents (42.0 percent) were 31 to less than 40 years old and above, with the majority (53.0 percent) being single, the remaining (31.3 percent) married, and a few (15.7 percent) separated/widowed. In addition, the proportion of participants (52.7 percent) had a university degree, led by those with a diploma (22.9 percent).

Table 4: Profile of respondents (N=402)

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	259	64.4
	Female	143	35.6
	Total	402	100.0
Age	less than 20	29	7.2
	21 to less than 30	71	17.7
	31 to less than 40	169	42.0
	41 to less than 50	106	26.4
	51 to less than 60	27	6.7

	Total	402	100.0
Status	Single	213	53.0
	Married	126	31.3
	Widow/ separated	63	15.7
	Total	402	100.0
Academic	high secondary school	98	24.4
	Bachelor	212	52.7
	Diploma	92	22.9
	Total	402	100.0

Measurement Model

This investigation included 36 items from four first-order components: EP, HRMs, LS, and EE. Confirmatory factor analysis was used to determine measurement models. The measuring model is demonstrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Path Model Results (p-value)

Convergent Validity

Table 5 illustrated the confirmatory factor analysis for the measurement model. The table demonstrates the findings and conclusions of the standardized factor loadings of the model's items. The standardized factor loadings have all been larger than 0.6, as indicated in the table. As can be seen, the loadings are in the range of 0.741 to 0.949. Furthermore, the AVE values for all constructions lie between 0.668 to 0.852. According to Hair et al. (2017), all percentages are larger than the cut-off value of 0.5. The composite reliability values for all constructions vary between 0.935 and 0.958, and as can be seen, the values are all more than 0.7, as recommended by Hair et al. (2017) and Fornell and Larcker (1981).

Table 5: Cronbach's Alpha and Convergent Validity Outcomes for the CFA Model on the Research Model

Variable	Items	Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE	
HRM Practices	Recruitment and Selection	R&E1	0.812	0.900	0.931	0.771
		R&E2	0.912			
		R&E3	0.892			
		R&E4	0.892			
	Training and Development	T&D1	0.879	0.884	0.920	0.743
		T&D2	0.897			
		T&D3	0.789			
		T&D4	0.877			
Rewards and Benefits	R&B1	0.867	0.866	0.909	0.714	
	R&B2	0.803				

Leadership style	Performance Appraisal	R&B3	0.893			
		R&B4	0.813			
		PA1	0.855	0.860	0.905	0.704
		PA2	0.889			
		PA3	0.852			
	Transformational Leadership	PA4	0.754			
		TFL1	0.901	0.893	0.926	0.758
		TFL2	0.869			
		TFL3	0.890			
	Transactional Leadership	TFL4	0.820			
		TAL1	0.840	0.863	0.907	0.710
		TAL2	0.853			
		TAL3	0.860			
		TAL4	0.815			
	Employee Engagement	EE1	0.862	0.925	0.944	0.770
		EE2	0.904			
EE3		0.891				
EE4		0.871				
EE5		0.859				
Employee Performance	EP1	0.771	0.900	0.924	0.669	
	EP2	0.871				
	EP4	0.863				
	EP5	0.878				
	EP6	0.720				
	EP7	0.793				

Discriminant validity

Depending on Henseler et al., (2016), this study produced HTMT to determine the discriminant validity of the model.

Table 6: The HTMT for constructs

Construct	HRM Practices	Leadership style	Employee Engagement	Employee Performance
HRM Practices				
Leadership Style	0.183			
Employee Engagement	0.738	0.216		
Employee Performance	0.827	0.277	0.844	

The Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) test was used to evaluate the discriminant validity of this investigation. The introduction of HTMT resulted from critiques of the Fornell-Larcker criterion in Smart PLS. The use of HTMT removes the constraints of the Fornell-Larcker criteria, which has an unsatisfactory low sensitivity and is incapable of detecting a lack of discriminant validity (Henseler et al., 2015). It is stated that if the HTMT value exceeds 0.85, there is a major problem with discriminant validity (Henseler et al., 2015). Table 6 indicates that the HTMT values for each latent variable were all less than 0.85 and ranged from 0.183 to 0.844. As a result, no discriminant validity exists.

Assessment Structural Model

The coefficient of determination (R^2) and path coefficients, which are both important in Hypotheses Testing, are included in structural model evaluation. As shown in Table 7, the R^2 values for the endogenous latent variables in this study reflect the guidelines of Schreiber, Nora, Stage, Barlow and King (2006), and it can be concluded that the structural model suggested in this study has predictive accuracy based on these values.

Table 7: The Endogenous Latent Variables' R^2 Values

Construct	R^2	Q^2
Employee Engagement	0.467	0.354
Employee Performance	0.714	0.470

Constructs' Hypothesized Direct Effects in a Structural Model

In this experiment, the PLS technique and bootstrapping approaches were utilized for path coefficients (Hypotheses Testing), utilizing Smart PLS rendition 3.2.8 and 5000 bootstrap datasets.

Table 8: Hypothesized Direct Effects of Structural Model

No.	Hypotheses	Beta	SE	T-Value	LL	UL	P-Value	Decision
H1	HRMP→EP	0.428	0.041	10.446	0.349	0.508	0.000	Supported***
H2	LS→EP	0.089	0.030	3.002	0.032	0.149	0.003	Supported**
H3	HRMP→EE	0.661	0.030	21.862	0.596	0.715	0.000	Supported***
H4	LS→EE	0.101	0.039	2.576	0.023	0.178	0.010	Supported*
H5	EE→EP	0.471	0.043	10.921	0.383	0.551	0.000	Supported***

As strongly advocated by Preacher and Hayes (2004), bootstrapping is increasingly being used to examine route coefficients. As a result, the current study employed the bootstrapping procedures included in SmartPLS (version 3.3.3) to determine if the route coefficients are statistically significant or not. The bootstrapping approach is used to evaluate the route coefficients, and a minimal bootstrap sample of 5000 is used (Hair et al., 2011). As illustrated in Table 8, the p-values and t-values corresponding among each route coefficient were computed using the bootstrapping technique (5000 resamples).

The Mediating Relationship Testing

Preacher and Hayes, (2013) employed the bootstrap approach in the present study to assess mediation using the bootstrapping techniques incorporated with SmartPLS (version 3.3.3). This approach is more effective and precise than others (Hair et al., 2014; Hayes & Scharkow, 2013; Zhao et al., 2010). It is anticipated in the mediation analysis section that employee engagement will mediate the relationship between human resource management practices and employee performance. Furthermore, Employee engagement in Jordanian tourist and archaeological enterprises is expected to mediate the relationship between leadership style and employee performance. The discovery showed that employee engagement significantly mediates the relationship between human resource management practices and employee performance (Path Coefficient = 0.312, T-Value = 9.215, P-Value = 0.000, LL = 0.246, UL = 0.379). Moreover, the discovery showed that employee engagement significantly mediates the relationship between leadership style and employee performance (Path Coefficient = 0.048, T-Value = 2.551, P-Value = 0.011, LL = 0.011, UL = 0.085). Hence, H6 and H7 are supported in this study. Table 9 shows the mediation relationship testing results.

Table 9: Results of mediating effects

No.	Hypothesis	Indirect Effect	Standard Error	T-value	P-value	Confidence Interval		Decision
						95% LL	95% UL	
H6	HRMP→EE→EP	0.312	0.034	9.215	0.000	0.246	0.379	Supported
H7	LS→EE→EP	0.048	0.019	2.551	0.011	0.011	0.085	Supported

***: $p < 0.001$; **: $p < 0.01$; *: $p < 0.05$; One tailed Hypothesis; 5,000 bootstrap samples

Figure 5: Path Model Significance Results (t-value)

Discussion

Theoretical Contribution

This study makes significant theoretical contributions to the literature on performance. This study adds to our understanding of the dynamic nature of performance. Prior studies have explicitly modeled change in employee performance, but this is one of the first longitudinal studies to evaluate its evolution over time, to the best of my knowledge. This study has offered information about how individuals fluctuate in performance at different times in time by collecting numerous waves of measurements from the same individuals. While no common pattern was seen for all participants, the findings support the hypothesis that performance evolves with time and that people grow differently. Knowledge of within-individual growth is crucial for making more accurate predictions about future performance and should be considered in future research and theory development.

The Social exchange theory (SET) and the resource-based theory (RBV) have not been evaluated for the existing framework in Jordan's tourism and archaeology industries. The current study looks at these theories in the context of tourism. It provides a new avenue for academicians and human resource managers (in academic settings) to develop policies to retain competent tourism industry and archaeological employees and improve their performance, allowing them to take an active role in gaining a competitive edge for tourist and archaeological services. This discovery is significant because it gave a more relevant and meaningful performance evaluation framework, especially for the tourism and archaeology industries. This is especially significant given the increasing prominence of performance studies in the hospitality field.

Practical Significance

The study's findings may be used by tourism and archaeological managers to better understand the performance of tourism and archaeological personnel who are engaged. According to the conclusions of this study, numerous elements such as social interactions with workplace reference groups (leaders and coworkers), HRMs, and employee engagement influence performance. Specific performance sources of motivation engage Jordanian employees differently.

The importance of the human resources department in the tourism and archaeology sectors cannot be overstated. The current study's findings indicate that HRMs and employee engagement have a substantial impact on the performance of tourism and archaeological sites. As a matter of fact, HR managers must prioritize the supply of improved HRMs in order to improve the quality of tourism and archaeological services by keeping skilled academic personnel. HRMs are one of the major incentives that contribute in enhancing the functioning of tourism and archaeological artefacts, according to the study's findings. Furthermore, training programs play an important part in enhancing competitive advantage. HR managers should concentrate on these four components, as well as the remaining HRM practices, in order to improve tourism and archaeological performance and compete with other sectors.

As per the findings, motivation is positively connected to employee performance. Managers should conduct thorough evaluations and considerations when hiring employees, attempting to discover and pick those that are diligent and accountable. According to the data, some employees utilize performance as a means of gauging employee engagement. Managers should offer positive feedback to those employees on the intended performance in a timely manner, and encourage them to participate more in tourism and archaeological performance.

Conclusion

In sum, the proposed hypotheses in this study were all supported. The results specifically found HRMs to positively influence employee performance indicating that positive HRMs in the minds of the employees about a tourist and archaeological would provide them greater efficiency and would affect their effectiveness towards it. In relation to this, the social exchange theory and practice have their basis on the actual benefits that employees as well as engagement via their relationships, with the objective being to maintain performance. Nevertheless, achieving successful relationships is quite challenging, and in this context, the present thesis contributes significantly to human resources literature by bringing forward a model that empirically examines the employees' perspectives among Jordanians of their relationship with tourist and archaeological management.

Therefore, the focal point of this study is enhancing tourist and archaeological performance in providing sustainable, high-quality service then achieving superior revenues with engaged, highly skilled employees by investing in HRMs, thus enhancing their role in fulfilling high organization performance. This study serves as a bridge to fill gaps in the previous researches. This study confirmed the RBV theory of Barney, (1991) and found that employee engagement has a significant effect on employee performance. The HRMs included in this model is focusing on increasing employee's ability, enhancing their motivation to perform as well as improving their opportunity for them to participate and be involved in the tourist and archaeological.

In conclusion, this study provides insights into the impact of HRMs on the employee performance of tourists and archaeological in Jordan with employee engagement as mediating role. Finally, suggestions were offered on the impact of Jordanian tourists and archaeological of HRMs, and employee engagement to achieve employee performance.

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Author Information

Hashem Tashtoush

Department of Maritime Studies, University Malaysia Terengganu (UMT), Malaysia

Norlinda Mohd Rozar

Department of Maritime Studies, University Malaysia Terengganu (UMT), Malaysia

Omar Shubailat

Department of Logistic Science, German Jordanian University (GJU), Jordan

Bandar Ersan Alown

Department of Logistic Science, German Jordanian University (GJU), Jordan

Aziz Madi

Department of Management Science, German Jordanian University (GJU), Jordan

